

Multi-paradigm Logic Programming in the \mathcal{E} rgoAI System: Supplement on Non-ground Negation

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1 Non-Ground Negation in \mathcal{E} rgo

\mathcal{E} rgo rules are evaluated using tabled resolution in which both goals and answers may be non-ground. Given \mathcal{E} rgo’s reliance on the well-founded negation within non-monotonic inheritance and argumentation, non-ground negation had to be addressed. Consider the resolution of the goal $p(?X)$ using the set of rules and facts in Figure 1. Since \mathcal{E} rgo uses a left-to-right literal selection strategy, the literal selected in Step 1 of the resolution is $q(?X)$, which substitutes $q(?X)$ with $\backslash\text{naf } q2(?X)$. Since it is a case of non-ground negation, \mathcal{E} rgo attempts to *delay* the evaluation of $\backslash\text{naf } q2(?X)$ in the hope that $?X$ will be grounded later on in the evaluation—for example, it conjectures that grounding of $?X$ might happen after resolving $r(?X)$.

The postponement is done using a slightly modified version of XSB’s `when/2` predicate, which delays the goal $\backslash\text{naf } q2(?X)$ until $?X$ becomes ground. This is shown on line 3 of the figure. The predicate `when/2` uses a feature called *attributed variables*, which underlie the evaluation of logical constraints in XSB and other Prologs. In the next step, $\backslash\text{naf } s(?Y)$ is selected and postponed, as shown on lines 4–5. Next, we resolve $r/1$ with the third rule and then with $r2(2)$, which finally binds $?X$ to 2, grounding the negative subgoal $\backslash\text{naf } q2(?X)$ to $\backslash\text{naf } q2(2)$. This is shown on lines 6–8. Since $\backslash\text{naf } q2(2)$ is true, we remove it, reaching line 9. Note that grounding of $\backslash\text{naf } q2(?X)$ was requested on line 3 but did not happen until line 8 after $r2(?X)$ got resolved. The two terms involved in this interaction, $\backslash\text{naf } q2(?X)$ and $r2(?X)$, do not even occur in the same rule! Moreover, when $\backslash\text{naf } q2(?X)$ got suspended, it was not even known whether $?X$ will ever get ground. The point is that the algorithm for subgoal delay is quite interesting, involves inter-rule interaction and run-time analysis, and goes well beyond just the `when/2` predicate. Limitation of space does not let us include it here, but it will be given in the full version. Here we just mention that subgoal delay is used in \mathcal{E} rgo also for many other interesting purposes.

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Program:

```

p(?X):- q(?X), \naf s(?Y), r(?X), t(?Z,?Y).
q(?X) :- \naf q2(?X).
r(?X) :- r2(?X).
q2(1). r2(2). s(3). t(4,?).

```

Evaluation of p(?X):

1. p(?X):- q(?X), \naf s(?Y), r(?X), t(?Z,?Y).
p(?X):- \naf s(?Y), r(?X), t(?Z,?Y), // delay q2/1
3. when(ground(?X),\naf q2(?X)).
4. p(?X):- r(?X), t(?Z,?Y), // also delay s/1
when(ground(?X),\naf q2(?X)), when(ground(?Y),\naf s(?Y)).
6. p(?X):- r2(?X), t(?Z,?Y), // r2/1 binds ?X to 2
when(ground(?X),\naf q2(?X)), when(ground(?Y),\naf s(?Y)).
8. p(2):- \naf q2(2), t(?Z,?Y), when(ground(?Y),\naf s(?Y)).
p(2):- t(?Z,?Y), when(ground(?Y),\naf s(?Y)).
10. p(2):- not_exists(s(?Y)). // fallback to XSB's well-founded not_exist/1
No // fail, since s(3) is true

Fig. 1. Schematic Evaluation of Non-Ground Default Negation

Resolving $t(?Z, ?Y)$ leaves a non-ground subgoal $\backslash\text{naf } s(?Y)$, which cannot be grounded later because the variable $?Y$ does not appear outside of that subgoal. How should one proceed? In our experience, in the overwhelming majority of such cases, the user wants to check whether *no grounding* of $?Y$ will ever make $s(?Y)$ true. This can be efficiently verified in XSB using the predicate `not_exists/1`, in lines 10 and 11 in the figure.¹ In a few cases, the user might want to assign the truth value *undefined* to non-ground $\backslash\text{naf}$ literals, such as $\backslash\text{naf } s(?Y)$. This option can be selected in *Ergo* via a runtime switch.

Our discussion has considerably simplified *Ergo*'s actions since the $\backslash\text{naf}$ operator also handles variables in *quantified* subgoals. Furthermore, it is generally accepted that $\backslash\text{neg } G$ implies $\backslash\text{naf } G$ [1], and this provides yet another way to ground $\backslash\text{naf}$ -negated subgoals. In short, many aspects of *Ergo*'s approach to $\backslash\text{naf}$ could be adopted by Prologs that implement WFS, such as XSB and SWI. In fact, nu-Prolog [2] implemented subgoal reordering for Prolog negation, although it was not able to assign the truth value *undefined* to non-ground negative subgoals, nor did it handle explicit negation or quantifiers.

References

1. Alferes, J., Damásio, C.V., Pereira, L.M.: A top-down query evaluation for well-founded semantics with explicit negation. In: ECAI. pp. 140–144. Morgan Kaufmann (1994)

¹ Roughly, XSB defines `not_exists(G)` as `(TG, fail ; tnot(TG))`, where `TG` is a certain tabled version of `G`, and `tnot/1` is the ground well-founded negation.

2. Naish, L., Dart, P., Zobel, J.: The NU-Prolog debugging environment. In: ICLP. pp. 521-536 (1989)